

Table 1. POE and peroxidase activity in chloroplasts (X) and cytoplasm (Y) in rice leaves, 42 d after transplanting, Ludhiana, India.^a

Mn applied (mg/kg)	POE		Peroxidase	
	A	B	X	Y
0	9	18	0.60	4.8
2.5	14	28	0.48	4.8
5.0	14	28	0.40	5.4
10.0	15	29	0.38	6.4
15.0	16	30	0.39	4.7
20.0	17	32	0.35	4.2

^aA = OD at 620 nm/unit chlorophyll per 5 min; B = OD at 620 nm/100 mg fresh wt per 5 min; X = OD at 660 nm/60 s per unit enzyme in chloroplast; Y = OD at 660 nm/60 s per 100 mg fresh wt in cytoplasm.

in a pot experiment. Four seedlings were transplanted per pot and Mn was applied at 0, 2.5, 5.0, 10.0, 15.0, and 20.0 mg/kg of soil. Chloroplasts were isolated from leaves 21 and 42 d after transplanting and colorimetrically assayed for photosynthetic oxygen evolution (POE). Peroxidase activity in chloroplasts and cytoplasm was determined colorimetrically using guaiacol as substrate. Results at two growth stages were similar. Data for the 42d stage are given here.

Table 2. Elemental composition in rice leaves, yield, and DTPA Mn in soil, Ludhiana, India.

Mn applied (mg/kg)	Composition (mg/kg)				Yield (g/pot)		DTPA Mn in soil (mg/kg)
	Mn	Fe	Fe ²⁺	Zn	Grain	Straw	
0	53	510	174	30	2.4	40	7.7
2.5	71	485	95	32	4.4	42	10.5
5.0	70	402	100	36	5.9	38	11.8
10.0	115	305	104	34	7.2	39	13.4
15.0	81	278	86	36	7.6	39	15.3
20.0	93	265	83	30	8.4	41	19.3

POE was very low in Mn-deficient plants but increased with application of 2.5 mg Mn/kg. Applying more Mn did not proportionately increase POE (Table 1). Chloroplast peroxidase was highest in plants that received no Mn. Cytoplasmic peroxidase increased up to 10 mg Mn/kg and decreased slightly at higher rates.

Elemental analysis of leaves showed Mn concentration increased with Mn supply (Table 2). Fe²⁺ and total Fe content in leaves was highest in 0 Mn plants, indicating an inverse relationship with Mn concentration. Zn concentration did not change with Mn

application.

Grain yield was significantly higher (about 4 times more with 20 mg Mn/kg than with 0 Mn) with Mn application, but straw yield was about the same. Grain filling was incomplete in Mn-deficient plants. DTPA Mn content 42 d after transplanting had increased manyfold in all pots due to reduction under submerged conditions.

Results indicate that although rice plants did not show symptoms of Mn deficiency, low Mn decreased photosynthetic activity and impaired translocation of photosynthates to grain. *ℓ*

The Na-K ratio as index of salt stress in rice cultures

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We screened 16 rices for salt tolerance in coastal soils in South Gujarat.

Grain yield, and K and Na content, and their ratios in different rices, Navsari, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	K (%)	Na (%)	Na:K
IET7587	2.6	0.51	1.05	2.06
IET7589	2.9	0.45	1.16	2.58
IET7908	1.8	0.36	1.05	2.92
IET7910	2.5	0.36	0.91	2.53
IET7911	2.3	0.32	0.91	2.84
IET6993	2.1	0.39	1.10	2.82
IET6996	2.6	0.40	1.17	2.92
IET7337	2.8	0.38	1.06	2.79
IET7588	3.4	0.52	0.99	1.90
IET7912	2.1	0.38	0.87	2.29
IR2031-729-2	3.5	0.57	0.68	1.19
SLR51214	2.8	0.40	1.04	2.60
CD at 5%	1.1	0.10	0.20	

SLR51214 was the check variety. At transplanting, soil had ECe 9.0 dS/m, pH 8.6, and ESP 25.

Twelve entries performed uniformly and at par with SLR51214. Grains were analyzed for nutrient content and Na:K was calculated (see table). K content varied from 0.32 to 0.57. IR2031-729-2 had highest K and lowest Na and yielded highest. Na:K for most varieties

was above 2.5. However, IR2031-729-2 had 1.19 and IET7588 had 1.90, indicating a preferential absorption of K over Na.

Yield and K content were highly and positively correlated ($r = 0.96$). The relation between yield and Na content was not significant. Na:K, however, was significantly and negatively correlated with yield ($r = -0.82$). *ℓ*

Azolla as a substitute for N fertilizer in rice cultivation

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In 1980-81 in Bhubaneswar, we studied azolla as a substitute for N fertilizer in rice cultivation. Soil was a laterite with pH 5.6, CEC 3.5 meq/100 g soil, 0.36% C, 0.35% N, 0.45% P, 1.55% K, 70.1%

sand, 16.3% silt, and 12% clay. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. All plots received 10 cartloads of farmyard manure, 13.3 kg P, and 24.9 kg K/ha before transplanting Pusa 2-21 (IR8/TKM6). Azolla was surface applied or multiplied in situ 1 wk before transplanting. Plots received azolla alone or azolla with urea fertilizer (see table).

All treatments yielded more than the control. Applying 10 t azolla/ha

Effect of azolla inoculation on rice yield, Bhubaneswar, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			Increase (%)
	1978-79 kharif	1979-80 kharif	1979-80 rabi	
Control	1.7	2.1	3.5	–
Azolla at 10 t/ha	2.1	3.0	4.6	34
Azolla at 1 t/ha, surface applied	1.9	2.6	4.2	20
Azolla at 5 t/ha + 15 kg N/ha	2.0	3.0	4.3	30
30 kg N/ha	2.1	3.0	4.6	34
60 kg N/ha	2.3	3.5	4.6	44
CD	0.4	0.6	0.6	

produced the same yield as 30 kg N/ ha. Highest yields were with azolla + urea. Applying azolla increased both total and available N. With 8 azolla crops in 1 season, total N harvest was about 140 kg/ ha at Bhubaneswar and 80 kg] ha in saline conditions. *ℒ*

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Effect of phosphorus on kharif rice

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We determined the P requirement of kharif rices in 1984 on soil with pH 7.8, EC 0.70 mmho/crn, 0.68% organic carbon, and 12.1 kg available P and 329 kg available K/ha. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. P at 0, 8.7, 17.5, and 26.2 kg/ ha applied basally as superphosphate were main plots; Swarna, Lakshmi, MTU7633, and Vasista were subplots. NK at 40-30 kg/ ha were applied to all treatments.

Swarna yielded highest with an average 5.3 t/ha, which was significantly

Grain and straw yields of 4 rices at 4 P levels, Maruteru, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)					Straw yield (t/ha)					
	0	8.7 kg	17.5 kg	26.2 kg	Mean	0	8.7 kg	17.5 kg	26.2 kg	Mean	
Swarna	5.1	5.2	5.4	5.5	5.3	6.1	5.9	6.2	6.2	6.1	
Lakshmi	4.0	3.8	4.1	4.3	4.1	5.0	5.0	4.9	5.1	5.0	
MTU7633	4.5	5.1	5.1	5.2	5.0	6.5	6.4	6.6	6.5	6.5	
Vasista	4.5	4.8	4.7	5.0	4.7	6.1	6.2	6.9	6.4	6.4	
Mean	4.5	4.7	4.8	5.0	4.8	5.9	5.9	6.2	6.0	6.0	
CD at 5%											
P levels						0.3	ns				
Varieties						0.2	0.2				
P levels × varieties						ns	ns				
Varieties × P levels						ns	ns				
CV%						4.8	3.7				

superior to that of all other varieties. P significantly increased yield only at 26.2 kg P/ ha (see table). P levels did not significantly influence straw yield.

MTU7633 had the highest mean straw yield of 6.5 t/ ha. Swarna performed best and 8.7 kg P/ha appears to be optimum and economical for the test varieties. *ℒ*

Storing Azolla pinnata inoculum for transport

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We evaluated different storage techniques for *A. pinnata*, Coimbatore strain. Fresh *A. pinnata* fronds were collected from field multiplication plots, soil was washed from their roots, and water was drained from them. The fronds were stored in cotton cloth, polyester cloth, newspaper, brown paper, polythene, polythene-lined gunny, and gunny bags for 5 d. Frond survival was recorded on days 2, 3, 4, and 5. All

Different bags for storing azolla, Coimbatore, India,

Treatment	Azolla survival (%)				Recovery (%) in the field when inoculated
	2d	3d	4d	5d	
Cotton cloth bag	100	58	45	19	26
Polyester cloth bag	100	53	40	17	17
Newspaper bag	100	57	56	19	21
Brown paper bag	100	41	38	16	15
Polythene bag	100	66	65	32	46
Polythene-lined gunny bag	100	62	46	28	27
Gunny bag	100	61	44	22	27
CD		5	5	2	4

azolla lived for 2 d, then began to die. At 5 d, polythene and polythene-lined

gunny bags performed best (see table). *ℒ*

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